

Morphological Study on Nine Species of the Family Poaceae from Some Area of East Bago Region

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Abstract

Poaceae is widely distributed family among the angiosperms. In these results, tribe Paniceae comprises 9 species and 7 genera of sub-family Panicoideae were collected in some area of East Bago Region. The morphological study on 9 species, 7 genera of sub-family Panicoideae are presented. Taxonomy descriptions are accompanied by the photographs of habits, ligules, inflorescences, spikelets and parts of the florets.

Keywords: Poaceae, East Bago Area

Introduction

All grasses belong to the family Poaceae (Gramineae) of order Poales. Presently there are about 780 genera and 12,000 species of grasses on the world and grass dominated ecosystem, including tropical and sub-tropical savannah, temperate grassland and steppe cover more than 30% of earth land surface (Willis, 2002). Poaceae are the fifth largest plant family (ESEAP Conference, 2018) in Myanmar, Poaceae is represented by 144 genera and 551 species according to Hundley and Chit Ko Ko, 1987. The appearance of grasses during the late Cretaceous and early tertiary also represent the earliest fossil evidence for wind-pollinated herbaceous monocotyledons. Most of grasses are very important economically and ecologically. In this present study, grasses from some area of East Bago Region. In this research presented the subfamily Panicoideae of family Poaceae are classified accordance with Hafliger and Scholz's classification (1981). 9 species and 7 genera were included in tribe Paniceae. Most genera of this tribe are well adaptation on land and aquatic habitats. They usually awnless, but awned with *Echinochloa* and *Oplismenus*. All of spikelets are usually only sessile, sub-sessile and pedicellate. Finally, this research present the subfamily Panicoideae and their modified characters, ranks variation of wild complex some grasses in some part of East Bago Region, Myanmar.

Materials and Methods

Collection, herbarium, identified, classified by Adonson (1963), Hooker (1885) Backer (1946), Bor (1960), Kurz (1974), Heywood (1993), Dassanayoke (1998), Jerne's Cullen (2000), Simpson (2000), Hong, Hafliger (1981), Herbarium (2007), Simon Gardener (2007) (2015).

Results (Morphology)

Scientific Name - *Panicum repens* Linn

Common Name - Myet-kha

Perennials, robust, culms up to 30-80 cm high, suberect or decumbent, spreading rhizomatous, nodes glabrous, leaf-blade linear-lanceolate, scabrous on upper surfaces ligule membranous, hairy at the mouth; leaf-sheath with one-side of margin ciliated. Inflorescences open panicles. Spikelet unequally pedicelled paired, narrowly lanceolate to ovate, creamish in color, about 3.0mm long, lower glume lanceolate, acuminate, about 2.0mm long, lower floret

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staminate, upper bisexual, upper lemma, coriaceous, upper palea membranous. Flowering and fruiting from May to January.

Fig 1. *Panicum repens* linn

Scientific Name - *Panicum auritum* Presl ex Nees

Common Name - Ye- saba- myet

Annual, tuft, culms up to 1.0 m high. Leaf-blade lanceolate; strigose on both surfaces, ligule membranous; long hairy at the mouth; leaf sheath with long hairs on one side of margins. Inflorescences lax panicle. Spikelet solitary; more than 1.5 mm long, pedicel scabrous, spikelet readily breaking up at maturity, 2-flowered; lower glume elliptic, half as long as the spikelet, 3-nerved, upper glume hyaline, 5-nerved, lower floret neuter, linear, lower lemma elliptic, lower palea very linear, upper floret bisexual, upper lemma and palea coriaceous. Flowering and fruiting from May to October.

Fig 2. *Panicum auritum* Presl.ex Nees

Scientific Name - *Echinochloa crusgalli* (L.)P.B

Common Name - Myet-cho

Aquatic annuals or short-lived perennials, culm up to 90cm high, node glabrous leaf-blade linear-lanceolate, both surface glabrous; ligule absent, leaf-sheath glabrous. Inflorescence rather compact and continuous racemously arranged panicles, rachis and pedicels triquetrous or sharply angular, densely scabrous to hispid on rachis surface. Spikelets broadly ovate-lanceolate, sessile, lower glume ovate, scabrous margins, acuminate, upper glume broadly lanceolate 5-nerved, lower floret neuter, lower lemma with 7 nerved; lower palea lanceolate, membranous, upper floret bisexual; upper lemma and palea broadly ovate, lemma with 3 obscure nerved, palea with 2-obscure nerved. Flowering and fruiting from May to January.

Habit

Inflorescence

Spike

Spikelets

Root

Fig 3. *Echinochloa crusgalli* (L.) P.B

Scientific Name - *Echinochloa colonum* (L.) LK.

Common Name - Be-sa-myet, Pa-zunsa

Annuals, culm prostrate to erect, up to 40cm high leaf-blade linear, glabrous on surfaces; scabrous on both margins, ligule obscure; leaf sheath glabrous. Inflorescence composed of racemes on a central axis, main axis and rachis with scabrous hairs. Spikelets groups on rachis, awnless, glumes with acuminate from middle nerves; lower glumes, cilia on the back of nerve, upper glume acuminate, 2-flowered, lower floret neuter, lower lemma ovate lanceolate, acuminate at the apex, lower palea very linear and upper bisexual, upper lemma broadly ovate, upper palea coriaceous, nerverless. Flowering and fruiting from April to October.

Fig 4. *Echinochloa colonum* (L.) LK.

Scientific Name - *Urochloa panicoides* P.Beauv
Common Name - Nil

Annuals, erect, tufted, culms 20cm high, node hairy. Leaf-blade linear-lanceolate, few hairs on both surfaces, tubercle-based hairs at the margin; ligule membranous fringed; leaf-sheath with hairy at the one side of margin. Inflorescences 2-3 sub-digitately arranged spikes. Spikelet solitary, ovate, lower glume ovate, 3-nerved, upper glume ovate, 11-nerved, pubescent on the back, lower floret elliptic, neuter, lower lemma elliptic, 5-nerved, pubescent on the back, lower palea elliptic, hyaline, keeled, 2-nerved, upper floret bisexual, upper lemma ovate, mucronate or very short awns, 3-nerved, crustaceous, upper palea elliptic. Flowering and fruiting from May to December.

Fig 5. *Urochloa panicoides* P. Beauv

Scientific Name - *Ottochloa nodasa* (kunth) Dandy

Common Name - Wayon- myet

Annuals, culms decumbent and creeping at base up to 60cm high leaf-blade lanceolate; glabrous on both surfaces; scabrescent at the margins; ligule membranous, truncate, leaf-sheath hairy on one side of margins. Inflorescences lax or open panicle. Spikelet solitary, dorsally compressed, not subtended by bristle- like branches, pedicelled, 2 flowered ; glumes unequal; lower glume elliptic-ovate, upper glumes much shorter than the spikelets, lower floret only present lemma, neuter, upper floret bisexual. Flowering and fruiting from May to December.

Habit

Inflorescence

Ligule

Spike

Spikelets

Stolon

Fig 6. *Ottochloa nodasa* (kunth) Dandy

Scientific Name - *Acroceras crassipiculatum* (Merr.) Alston

Common Name - Nil

Annuals, creeping or decumbent based culms, node glabrous. Leaf-blade lanceolate to linear, glabrous; ligule membranous fringed; leaf-sheath one side of margin with pilose. Inflorescences closely spikelet distant arranged on the panicle or spike-like racemes. Spikelet readily breaking up from pedicels. Spikelet elliptic-ovate, laterally compressed, up to 2.2 mm long, lower glume ovate, 2-to 3-nerved, upper glume ovate, 5-nerved, lower floret neuter, lower lemma ovate, 5-nerved, upper floret bisexual, upper lemma ovate, 3-nerved, slightly obscure, upper palea ovate, 1.5 mm long, nerveless, stamens 2, grain ellipsoid. Flowering and fruiting from May to October.

Fig 7. *Acroceras crassipiculatum* (Merr.) Alston

Scientific Name - *Axonopus compressus* (Sw.)P.B.

Common Name - Hgnet-daw-ni, Carpet- grass

Perennial or erect, tufted, stoloniferous spreading. Culms 15.0- 50.0cm long, the nodes with white hairy, leaf-blades lanceolate, hairy on the upper surface. Inflorescences composed of 2-3 ascending spike-like racemes, sub-digitately arranged. Spikelets solitary, elliptic, 2.0-3.0mm long, 2-flowered; glumes unequal, the lower glumes absent, the upper glumes elliptic- oblong, awnless, hyaline, acuminate at the apex, 4-6nerved, hairy on the back; lower florets ovate-elliptic, awnless, sessile, neuter, the lemmas ovate-elliptic, awnless, hyaline, acute at the apex, 4-nerved, hairy on the back, keeled, paleas absent, upper floret ovate elliptic, awnless sessile, bisexual, the paleas elliptic, awnless, crustaceous, acute at the apex, 2-nerved, keeled the lodicules 2. Flowering and fruiting from April to January.

Fig 8. *Axonopus compressus* (Sw.)P.B.

Scientific Name - *Oplismenus compositus* (L.) P.B.

Common Name - Myet-let-the

Perennials, small, slender, stoloniferous, the whole culm with woolly hairs, culms up to 10.0 -90.0 cm long, nodes hairy. Leaf-blade lanceolate-oblong , puberulous on upper surfaces, velutinous on lower surfaces, strongly scabrous on both margins; ligule hairy ring; long hairs at the mouth; both side of margins with long hairs; Inflorescences composed of racemes borne a central axis, up to 15.0cm long, main axis and rachis with densely woolly hairs terminal portions more delicate and dense haris. Spikelets paired and alternately arranged on the rachis, linear-lanceolate, about 2.5 cm long (excluding awned), lower glume elliptic, awned, 5-nerved, upper glume elliptic-ovate, awned, lower floret neuter, lower lemma broadly ovate, 11-nerved, upper floret bisexual, upper lemma broadly ovate, 5-nerved, upper palea elliptic, 2-nerved. Flowering and fruiting from May to January.

Fig 9. *Oplismenus compositus* (L.) P.B

**Location Map of Study Area
(Some Area of East Bago Region)**

Discussion and Conclusion

The grass family Poaceae (Gramineae) is one of the largest in number of genera and species. In this present study, 9 species, 7 genera in subfamily Panicoideae of family Poaceae are Systematically arranged according to Hafliker and Schotz classification (1981). The large tribe Paniceae of subfamilies Panicoideae is a strongly dominant in study area. It is a deciduous 2 flowered spikelets with a barren on neuter or staminate form pattern of minute lower flower. In this result, 9 species and 7 genera of tribe Paniceae were presented. Genus *Panicum* is open to contrasted panicle and usually fertile upper and staminate lower florets. The aquatic and terrestrial habitats species of genus *Panicum*, are very differ from each other. Genus *Echinochloa* is distinctly long awned to awnless modified lemma. Upper and lower florets all fertile.

Genera of *Eriochloa*, *Acroceras*, and *Urochloa* are strongly growing in aquatic to land adaptation. Genera of *Ottochloa*, *Oplismenus* are likely in shady places. *Oplismenus* with distinct awned upper glume. Genera of *Axonopus* are digitately inflorescences type. *Axonopus* is awn grass and is usually 2-3 digitate branch and glabrous leaf- sheath, their variation inflorescences and spikelet shape, size, leaf differences root and rhizome. Above these taxonomic wild grasses research identified, classified and detail description unit were agree with the accordance citation of Bor, Clayton, Cronquist, Hafliker, Hooker, Hundley and Willis. This reasearch support the partially point of view in some area of East Bago Region wild grasses in Myanmar. Finally, the taxonomic study of grasses would use more convenient after the meaning of the terms and words used in the description had been understood in advance.

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